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A glimpse of optimism for Lebanon's public (rail) transport: donation of 50 buses by France!

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ABSTRACT

Lebanon is currently experiencing a manifold of crises, the worst since the Civil War (1975-1990) that crippled the country and its people, among them a suffocating financial crisis – the worst economic and financial crisis that the world has seen since 1850, according to the World Bank. It is destroying the livelihoods and lives of the people of Lebanon, and also affects whatever public transport there is in this country – it is virtually non-existent. With respect to the latter, on 23 May 2022, a slight glimmer of hope appeared on the horizon, when a ship arrived at the Port of Beirut, carrying a first batch of the 50 buses that have been donated by France. This paper addresses this issue and looks at the challenges and opportunities for Lebanon's road transport sector.

1. INTRODUCTION

The UN Habitat for Humanity published a report on Transport and Mobility in 2021, stating that the transport sector in Lebanon is one of the most unsustainable in the Middle East region, owing to weak governance structures and regulatory frameworks, the lack of a modern and reliable public transportation system, and a car-friendly culture dominated by large, old-model polluting cars. Further, the report concluded that Lebanon lacks a comprehensive and inclusive transportation system, with mostly informal public transportation and very limited infrastructure for alternative modes of transportation (UN-Habitat, 2021a).

In 2017, the United Nations Human Settlements Programme in Lebanon launched the National Urban Policy (NUP) program to assist in the management of the country's rapid urbanization, capitalizing on opportunities and addressing stresses. Lebanon's program, which is part of a regional program that also includes Jordan, Tunisia, and Sudan, reached a significant milestone in 2018 with the publication of a diagnosis report (UN-Habitat Lebanon, 2018). This included completing the diagnosis phase of a five-phase NUP process (Figure 1) that concentrated on feasibility, diagnosis, formulation, implementation, monitoring and evaluation. Consultations with relevant stakeholders following the publication of the diagnosis report identified transportation as one of two sectors, along with housing, that are particularly important for the country's sustainable urban development.

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Figure 1. The NUP process

2. MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING

As noted earlier, Lebanon lacks an integrated and inclusive transportation system, with most public transportation being informal and very limited infrastructure for alternative modes of transportation such as walking and cycling. As a result, mobility is concentrated on car use on congested highways, with high consumption of polluting fossil fuels, making Lebanon's road transport sector the second largest energy consumer and having long-term effects on human health and the environment. Furthermore, the authorities in charge of managing the sector have unclear responsibilities and limited resources, limiting the sector's potential for proper development toward greater accessibility, efficiency, and effectiveness.

The establishment of a NUP for Lebanon may thus provide an opportunity to improve the planning, implementation, and integration of new transportation infrastructure, technologies, and service models into appropriate urban forms, allowing people easy access to a variety of transportation modes. This will allow urban residents to reach more destinations, opportunities, and amenities in a safe, convenient, and cost-effective manner, potentially improving living quality in Lebanese cities. This can also contribute to economic prosperity and growth by attracting new businesses and investments.

2.1 Donation of 50 buses by France

On 11 March 2022, as part of an integrated transportation plan, the French government signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with Lebanon, under which France would donate 50 public transport buses to Lebanon, in order to modernize the Lebanese public transport network, and also to supplement the some 40 buses that are currently circulating the roads (Figure 2) (The Daily Star, 2022]. On 23 May 2022, the first shipment of buses arrived at the Port of Beirut (Figure 3).

The MoU signed between France and Lebanon also entails that France would provide “technical assistance and expertise” and “in-depth reflection on the organization and structuring of urban transport in Lebanon.” Thus, the donation of the 50 buses is part of a bigger initiative to improve Lebanon’s transportation sector. According to the MoU, Lebanese authorities are to establish a fund, financed by donations that are to be obtained from other countries, in order to financially assist passengers in paying their fares.

About one-third of the donated buses are to serve the Greater Beirut Area (GBA), and the remainder is destined for operation in the Beqaa Valley, and North and South Lebanon. Each of the donated single-deck buses could offer space for up to 92 passengers, a big improvement as compared to the 24-seater buses that are currently in operation. It is expected, that once financial support is in place, the donated buses could somewhat alleviate the dire public transport system in Lebanon, but they are insufficient to solve the entire problem. The construction of railway lines and/or a SkyWay system is also of paramount importance.

Figure 2. Signing of Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) on 11 March 2022
– involving France's donation of 50 buses –
by the French Transport Minister Delegate, Mr. Jean-Baptiste Djebbari (left)
and the Lebanese Minister of Public Works & Transport, Mr. Ali Hamieh (right),
with the (now caretaker Lebanese Prime Minister, Mr. Najib Mikati, looking on (centre)

Figure 3. Arrival of the first batch of donated buses at the Port of Beirut

3. OVERVIEW OF CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR LEBANON'S ROAD TRANSPORT SECTOR

Road transport activity in Lebanon has grown rapidly and steadily over the last two decades, in tandem with population and economic growth, until the onset of the 2019 economic crisis and the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. However, the increase in travel activity has not been matched by the development of the necessary infrastructure and services. In fact, no progress on public transportation has been made by government authorities or the private sector since the end of Lebanon's 15-year civil war in 1990, and there have been no major initiatives to promote and enable alternatives to motorized transport in cities or across the country in general. This has contributed to severe traffic congestion in cities and across the country, making Lebanon's transportation sector one of the least sustainable in the Middle East (Haddad et al., 2015). The challenges of road passenger transport in Lebanon, as well as the opportunities for improvement, are described in the following subsections through a plethora of observations and data.

3.1 High rates of motorization and severe traffic congestion

Mobility in Lebanon is almost entirely dependent on motorized transport, with approximately 1.49 million cars for passenger travel, over 150,000 light-duty vehicles (LDVs) and heavy-duty vehicles (HDVs) for passenger and freight movement, including buses for public transportation and trucks for goods movement, and over 100,000 motorcycles, for a total of approximately 1.75 million registered

vehicles (MoIM, 2015). This corresponds to a distribution of approximately 85% for passenger cars, 0.9% for buses, 7.9% for LDVs and HDVs, and 6.2% for motorcycles (Figure 4). With a 2015 population of approximately 5.5 million (excluding Syrian refugees in border areas), this translates into a share of more than 270 cars per 1,000 people, or approximately 1 passenger car for every 3.7 people, placing Lebanon among the most motorized countries in the Middle East. This is largely due to a lack of alternatives to car use on the one hand, and the availability of financial facilities in the form of low-interest car loans by banks and financing institutions on the other (until the beginning of the ongoing financial crisis). These are aided by the government's economic policy of pegging the local currency to the US dollar at a fixed exchange rate for the past three decades (until currency exchange fluctuations began in late 2019 and eventually led to de-pegging), making passenger car purchases less affordable.

Figure 4. Registered vehicles in Lebanon (MoE, UNDP and GEF, 2016)

3.2 Main challenges facing the urban planning system

According to the UN-Habitat diagnosis report that provided a context analysis for Lebanon from social, economic, and political perspectives, using three key thematic areas: urban legislation, urban economy, and urban planning and design, the main challenges facing the urban planning system in Lebanon were identified as follows (UN-Habitat Lebanon, 2018):

- Lack of communication and inconsistency between the national and local levels.
- Absence of integrated planning in the urban management system.
- Centralized and hierarchical administrative system of Lebanon.
- Poor appreciation of the concerns and interests of stakeholders, beneficiaries, and related end users.
- Lack of public participation in urban planning.
- Inefficiency of some urban planning laws, rules, and regulations.
- Lack of inter-organizational relationships.
- Expansion of urban areas, as well as issues related to urban sprawl and informal settlements.

3.3 Lebanon's transport challenges

Lebanon lacks an integrated and inclusive transportation system, with mostly informal public transportation and very limited infrastructure for alternative modes of transportation like walking and cycling. Thus, mobility is concentrated on car use on congested highways, with high consumption of polluting fossil fuels, making Lebanon's road transport sector the second largest consumer of energy and having long-term effects on human health and the environment. Furthermore, the national and local government authorities in charge of managing the sector have unclear responsibilities and limited resources, limiting the sector's potential for proper development toward greater accessibility, efficiency, and effectiveness.

3.4 Energy, environmental and health impacts

The rise in demand for motorized mobility translates into increased energy consumption in road transport, which in Lebanon is overwhelmingly powered by fossil fuels, with gasoline and diesel accounting for about 99% of CO emissions (Figure 5). Consumption levels rise even more in gridlocked traffic, not only because a trip takes longer to complete, but also because of slower driving speeds and longer idling periods, both of which result in the inefficient operation of conventional internal combustion engines (ICEs). Furthermore, because of the inefficiency of their outdated engine technologies, older vehicle models, which dominate the Lebanese vehicle fleet, with over 70% of cars older than 10 years, are responsible for higher energy consumption. Larger vehicle types, which account for more than 60% of the Lebanese passenger car fleet, also contribute to an increase in energy consumption due to their large (over 2.0 liters) gas-guzzling engines (MoE, URC and GEF, 2012). As a result of these factors, road passenger transportation in Lebanon has a high energy demand per capita, estimated in 2007 at 15.06 GJ per capita, which exceeds the global average. And, as more fuel is consumed, more emissions are released into the atmosphere, including greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (primarily carbon dioxide [CO₂]), which are a major contributor to global warming and climate change, as well as pollutant emissions, which have a negative impact on human health. Indeed, the transportation sector in Lebanon is the second largest source of total GHG emissions, accounting for more than 23% of total annual GHG emissions, and is a major polluter, accounting for 95% of total carbon monoxide (CO), 60% of total nitrogen oxide (NO_x), and 57% of total non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOCs) (MoE, UNDP and GEF, 2016).

Figure 5. Transport sector emissions (MoE, UNDP and GEF, 2016)

The issues are particularly acute in dense urban areas with slow-moving traffic on typically narrow streets, as well as suburban areas adjacent to major highways, where mobility has become synonymous with noxious fumes and a primary cause of respiratory and other diseases, as well as a source of stress, loss of productivity, and waste of disposable income. Despite the dire environmental consequences, there is hope for progress thanks to the country's commitment to reduce emissions under the 2016 Paris Agreement signed by parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). Indeed, Lebanon has committed to reducing its GHG emissions by at least 15% by 2030 compared to 2010. (MoE, 2015). This will be accomplished by providing incentives to renew the vehicle fleet with fuel-efficient vehicles (FEVs) and hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs) in order to achieve a market share of 35% and 10%, respectively, by 2040, and by revitalizing the public transportation system in order to increase its share of passenger kilometers (pass-km) travelled by bus by 15%.

3.5 Inadequate bus system and absence of rail

Lebanon's public transportation system was largely destroyed during the country's civil war, which lasted from 1975 to 1990. As a result, the railway system, which consists of approximately 400 kilometers of installed rail and nearly 30 stations serving four rail lines along Beirut-Damascus, Naqoura-Tripoli, Tripoli-Homs, and Rayak-Aleppo, became completely inoperative, and all attempts to revive it have failed. Similarly, a single attempt in the late 1990s to revitalize the public bus system with the purchase of 200 newer-model buses was short-lived, and the public bus system has been reduced to less than 40 old-model buses operating on nine lines to serve a population of more than 2 million people in the GBA and surrounding areas (Baaj, 2002). There are no other public transportation options in Lebanon, such as a marine ferry or internal aviation flights. To date, exclusive-use taxis and shared-ride taxis (known as "service taxis"), as well as newer ride hailing providers such as Uber and Careem, account for the majority of mass transportation in Lebanon, with a low vehicle occupancy rate of 1.2 passengers per vehicle (Figure 6). Private minivans and buses account for the remaining market share, with estimated occupancies of 6 and 12 people per van and bus, respectively. These operate ad hoc, with no fixed routes, schedules, stops, or stations, no coordination or central management, and only basic information provided by third parties in the form of paper maps and non-real-time mobile applications. There are also no measures, equipment, or infrastructure in place to make public transportation accessible to the elderly, people with disabilities, or other vulnerable groups.

Figure 6. Vehicle occupancy rates for mass transport in Lebanon (MoE, URC and GEF, 2012).

As a result, by international standards, public transportation in Lebanon is considered unreliable, uncomfortable, and unsafe, limiting ridership and forcing commuters to continue relying on private automobiles. This is a major contributor to the country's unsustainable land transport sector, as illustrated in Figure 5, which compares cities around the world based on the modal share of private cars versus GDP per capita. This places Beirut alongside car-dependent cities with the highest rates of urban sprawl, such as some cities in North America and Australia. However, what makes Beirut's position even more untenable is the lack of viable alternatives offered by American and Australian cities, such as buses and rail, as well as the lack of necessary resources for long-term system improvement, as is the

case in Riyadh, where major public transportation projects, such as buses, metros, and monorails, are underway.

This unsustainable reality is due, in large part, to a lack of vision and strategy required for proper city planning and development in Lebanon, as well as administrative mismanagement of the public transportation system. This has hampered all CSO and international agency modernization efforts, leaving the market to be dominated by private operators, many of whom operate without a proper license. Unofficial figures show that 33% of taxi licenses (known as "red plates") are illegal, resulting in anti-competitive practices among operators. Furthermore, Lebanon's public transportation system remains unregulated, which leads to chaotic operations and contributes to traffic jams rather than alleviating congestion—an unusual role due to the lack of dedicated lanes and irregular pick-up and drop-off patterns that increase traffic collision risks and casualties.

3.6 Lack of walking, bicycling spaces, traffic calming measures, and poor road safety

The majority of Lebanon's cities have become unfriendly to cyclists and pedestrians. The most notable is Beirut, where ad hoc and unchecked urbanization has occurred (UN-Habitat Lebanon, 2021b), making it difficult to commute by any mode of transportation, particularly walking and cycling. Some of the primary causes of these difficulties are:

- There is no use of zoning or land-use planning in Lebanon to encourage walking and cycling. As a result, there are few pedestrian-only zones in the GBA and other cities, with only a few car-free days in select areas.
- A lack of sidewalks alongside most roadways, as well as a poor state of use for the majority of those that do exist, in addition to common infringement by cars parked over most sidewalks and random obstructions, such as unofficial signposts and barriers, for illegally reserving curbside parking spots in front of residential buildings and commercial establishments.
- A lack of clearly marked pedestrian crosswalks at intersections, as well as pedestrian walkways, bridges, tunnels, and other structures to allow for safe pedestrian crossing of roadways.
- There are few parks and public squares for walking, bicycling, and scootering, and the few that do exist have become inaccessible to the public due to security measures.
- There are no dedicated bike lanes in or around the GBA, only temporary bike trails in limited areas are made available for biking on occasion. A 3-kilometer bike lane with traffic (separated only by roadway markings) was installed in the city of Tripoli to the north of Beirut in 2016, and a dedicated bike trail was installed in the city of Byblos to the north of Beirut in 2019.
- Only one operational bike-sharing system was installed in Byblos, to the north of Beirut, in 2017, with only a handful of bikes available. A few similar bike-sharing systems were installed in the GBA in 2018, but have yet to be operational; some have even been removed in recent months due to political and economic instability.
- Dominance of highways and roadways over urban space, which cut off the residential areas of parts of Beirut from each other and the city center.
- Some traffic-calming measures, particularly speed bumps on internal roads to slow traffic in residential and commercial areas, are widely used in Lebanon. However, these measures almost never include urban land-use planning and regulations, which are most effective for calming traffic and reducing car dependence—for example, changing street design standards to create pedestrian-only spaces with services such as shopping and recreational activities. At the same time, the chronic lack of enforcement of traffic laws encourages motorists to drive recklessly and at high speeds, endangering cyclists and pedestrians and discouraging alternative modes of transportation.

3.7 Expensive mobility and a lack of innovative mobility options

In 2015, the cost of motorized mobility in Lebanon was estimated to range between USD 0.43 and USD 0.64 per vehicle-kilometer traveled for small-size vehicle categories, and USD 0.64 for large-engine sport utility vehicles (SUVs). Given that the average regular commuter in Lebanon drives 12,000 km per year, or approximately 33 km per day, the daily cost of mobility would be LBP 21,000 (at the current official exchange rate of USD 1 = LBP 1,500). As a result, mobility in Lebanon can be viewed as a significant financial burden on commuters.

However, with the significant and ongoing depreciation of the Lebanese Pound since 2019, which has increased all vehicle-related costs by multiple orders of magnitude, in line with the rate of unofficial trading of the US dollar in the market, it has become quite clear that motorized mobility is becoming completely unsustainable.

Most of these major cost components can be mitigated, at least in large part, by proper urban and transport planning policies and strategies aimed at reducing motorized vehicle trips and commuting distances. Such measures would directly lower travel time, congestion, fuel consumption, and emissions, and indirectly lower the risk of accidents. Therefore, there is an urgent need to find new solutions for affordable, reliable, and safe mobility in the country, especially since the transport sector is the backbone of the Lebanese economy—for touristic, industrial, and/or agricultural activities.

3.8 Fragmented institutional and regulatory framework

In Lebanon, several governmental institutions have different types of authority over the transport sector, including the authority to regulate, implement, operate, manage, and oversee various parts of the sector. The main entities and their agencies are (Figure 7):

- **Ministry of Public Works and Transport (MoPWT)**, namely the following directorates:
 - **The Directorate General of Land and Maritime Transport (DGLMT)** is responsible for the organization, administration, and oversight of the entire land transport sector and its proper development, as well as oversight of public transport services.
 - **The RPTA (also known as Office des Chemins de Fer et des Transports en Commun or OCFTC)** is part of the MoPWT but operates as an independent body in charge of managing and operating the railway and public bus networks.
 - **The Directorate General of Roads and Buildings (DGRB)** is responsible for the construction, rehabilitation, and maintenance of the public roadway network.
 - **The Directorate General of Urban Planning (DGUP)** is mandated to develop and review national urban master plans and regulations for urban planning. It presides over the Higher Council of Urban Planning (HCUP), which is a coordination mechanism between concerned ministries and agencies.
- **Ministry of Interior and Municipalities (MoIM)**, namely the following organizations:
 - **The Traffic Management Organization (TMO)** is in charge of developing traffic and parking operating plans and overseeing the implementation of traffic laws.

- **The Traffic and Vehicle Management Authority (TAVMA)**, which is included in the TMO, is in charge of vehicle registration and inspection, driver licensing, and traffic code implementation.
 - **The Council for Development and Reconstruction (CDR)** reports directly to the Council of Ministers and receives funds separately from donors. It is responsible for roadway planning and project implementation. It is also mandated to develop master plans for urban planning.
 - **Municipalities** are in charge of roads within their municipal jurisdiction and the associated regulation of traffic. The different institutions and their associated responsibilities were outlined in detail during the diagnosis phase of Lebanon's NUP (UN-Habitat Lebanon, 2018).
- **The Ministry of Finance (MoF)** is responsible for the allocation and disbursement of funds for the implementation of the majority of transport projects by ministries and municipalities.

As illustrated in Figure 7, there is no centralized authority in charge of the land transportation system, which is the primary reason for the lack of a comprehensive national transportation strategy or a road map for sustainable mobility. The distribution of responsibilities among various stakeholders, sometimes with overlapping mandates, results in conflicting plans and decisions, delays in action implementation, and ultimately gridlocked outcomes. Furthermore, there is a lack of coordination between agencies, even within the same ministry; a lack of integration of project activities across different ministries' funding, implementing, and operating agencies; and a complete lack of comprehensive urban transportation and land-use planning. For example, different institutions may carry out various aspects of the same project without detailed coordination or clear communication with the public.

4. AN EFFICIENT AND MODERN PUBLIC TRANSPORT SYSTEM

Building more roads, demolishing buildings to make space for more cars, and adding more parking spaces will only exacerbate the road traffic congestion problems in Beirut. Anyway, in the case of Beirut, decreasing road traffic congestion by developing more roads is not a viable option, because of its urban density and terrain, with the mountains to one side, the sea to another, and a narrow coastal strip in-between. Any road development project would require either the expropriation of land, or the construction of tunnels in mountains or highways over the sea, all of which would be costly options. This leaves the development of an efficient and modern public transport system as the only and most favorable option.

As noted in numerous articles (e.g., Choueiri, 2014; Choueiri, 2018; Choueiri, 2020; Choueiri, 2021), studies to implement an efficient and modern public transport system to alleviate road traffic congestion in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA) have been underway for several years now, but are struggling to make much progress due to the various political, economic, financial, and other crises Lebanon is currently plagued with. Among these studies are railways, such as revitalizing railway services (using existing rights-of-way) on the following routes:

- Beirut - Jounieh - Tabarja-Maameltein (- Tripoli); and
- Tripoli - Abboudiyeh.

Model/function/process	Roads	Traffic management	Parking	Public transport	Paratransit	Freight	Accidents	Urban transport	Vehicle registration	Rail transport
Policy	DGRB	TAVMA DGRB		DGLMT	DGLMT			DGLMT		DGLMT
Regulation	DGRB	TAVMA DGRB	DGU	DGLMT	DGLMT	DGLMT	DGRB		MoM TAVMA	RPTA
Planning	DGRB CDR		TAVMA	RPTA						
Financing	MoF CDR	MoF CDR		RPTA MoF			MoF CDR			
Project preparation & implementation	DGRB CDR Municipalities						DGRB CDR Municipalities			RPTA
Operation management		Municipalities	MoM TAVMA	RPTA			DGRB Municipalities			
Maintenance management	DGRB	Municipalities	MoM TAVMA	RPTA			DGRB Municipalities			
User information		MoM TAVMA	MoM TAVMA				MoM TAVMA		MoM TAVMA	

Figure 7. Government functional responsibilities for land transport (MoE, UNDP and GEF, 2016)

Another option to consider is an elevated SkyWay system between Beirut Rafic Hariri International Airport and Casino du Liban (Jounieh) with intermediate stations at key locations. Such a system could alleviate the serious road traffic congestion situation near the airport and, thus, provide an efficient and reliable transport alternative for people travelling to/from the airport, as well as other destinations served by this route.

For any of the aforementioned to become a reality, it would take quite some time. However, the dire road traffic congestion situation needs to be alleviated much sooner—a temporary solution could come in the form of the Greater Beirut Urban Transport (GBUT) project. GBUT entails the establishment of appropriate institutional entities for the management, operation, and maintenance of the BRT system. Once implemented, it would become Lebanon’s first modern public transport system in decades. France's donation of 50 buses is seen as a first tentative step toward getting the GBUT system up and

running. Without a dedicated BRT corridor, buses would be trapped in mixed traffic, with no dedicated stations for passengers or regulated timetables. Finally, it is expected that there will be no improvement in the level of service provided by a public transportation system, with negative consequences for quality of life and the environment. As an alternative to ground-level structures, BRT corridors running through the median highway can be built on separate elevated roads or underground viaducts. Because of the complexity of the underground system and the archaeological potential in Lebanon, an elevated system must be considered as a potential alternative to the current project.

5. FUNDING NEEDED

With the financial and economic situation in Lebanon being very much in a dilapidated state, the country is very much in need of financial support for—actually—everything, including projects to alleviate its road traffic congestion situation. In March 2018, the World Bank approved a USD 295 million financial package to allow the alleviation of some of the imminent problems facing the road transport sector in Lebanon, and, at a later stage, it extended a preliminary agreement to institutionally and financially support the aforementioned Greater Beirut Urban Transport (GBUT) project (World Bank, 2018). However, due to the ongoing economic collapse of the country, which started in October 2019, the project, once hailed to be the country's "first modern transportation system" in decades, has not yet materialized!

6. CONCLUDING REMARKS

As noted earlier, the USD 295 million financial package for the road transport sector, approved by the World Bank, was never disbursed, because it was tied to the government demonstrating progress in implementing economic reforms, including improving fiscal management. Of course, any donor would want to see a genuine and lasting commitment to seeing reforms through in Lebanon. That means setting up a credible and transparent follow-up mechanism to monitor progress, not just government pledges of improved management, given Lebanon's poor record in terms of fiscal responsibility and capital investment, as well as the country's poor infrastructure. Donors and investors will need to be convinced that Lebanon is really in a position to implement infrastructure projects in an effective manner as, in the past, weak governance standards have allowed sectarian and elite interests too much influence in the awarding of public contracts. So, it is really up to the political leaders of Lebanon to capitalize on the goodwill of the international community that is willing to offer financial support, but only when requested reforms are in place and protected.

However, at the time of writing this article, there has been no government in place in Lebanon since the parliamentary elections held in May 2022. There is only a caretaker government, which, although very much attempting to do what it can, is very much restricted in its actions. To further exacerbate the situation, as of 1 November 2022, Lebanon does not have a president, as Members of Parliament (MPs) have not been able/willing to agree on a successor to the previous one. Both are needed to take the country further on its long journey to implement the reforms necessary to unlock funding from external bodies [e.g., the World Bank, the European Union (EU), the European Investment Bank (EIB), and the United Nations' Development Programme (UNDP)], so that the various (public) transport projects can finally go ahead.

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